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**CAIRT measurement requirements assessment
Technical note on analog-digital discretization error**

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<p>The uncertainty introduced by analog-digital conversion through bit-discretization of read-out interferograms on the retrieved vertical profiles of temperature and trace gas species is investigated.</p>		
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1. Introduction

The uncertainty introduced by analog-digital conversion through bit-discretization of read-out interferograms on the retrieved vertical profiles of temperature and trace gas species is investigated.

2. Method

- Use one limb-sequence of spectra from ERS spectral database (April 45N day) (atm) (Figure 1, left column, top two graphs show the highest and lowest altitude spectra)
- Apply assumed (negative, this is arbitrary since the real instrumental background is not known) instrument background T (10 and 240K, Figure 1, left column, bottom, to test sensitivity to background radiance) (here: spectra = atm – planck(Tinstr)) (Figure 1, middle column)
- Assume DC-level (here: 2*max(IFG(planck(Tinstr)))) (Figure 1, right column)
- Assume number of A-D pixels in one row (112 and 12, 12: the number of 25-km wide sub-sample to reach the threshold swath-width of 300 km)
- Calculate NESR-spectrum (scaled to number of A-D pixels) (Figure 3). For NESR, the threshold values of the measurement requirements are used.
- Perform FT(spectra+noise) (=IFG(spectra+noise) and add DC-level
- Perform A-D 'conversion' such that the IFG-range belonging to the lowest limb-view (IFG_{lowest}) is discretized by 14 or 16 bit (=nbit):

$$\text{fac} = 2^{\text{nbit}} / \max(\text{IFG}_{\text{lowest}})$$

$$\text{IFG}_{\text{AD}} = \text{round}(\text{fac} * \text{IFG}) / \text{fac}$$
- FT of the IFG(spectra+noise) and A-D converted IFG(spectra+noise) from previous bullet
- Coadd resulting (here: 12 and 112) spectra to obtain spectra for 300 km track-width
- Calculate error spectra by difference to reference (Figure 4), i.e. reference are the spectra FT(IFG(spectra+noise))
- Use error spectra in linear error analysis

Figure 1 From atmospheric spectra (left, top 115 km, middle 5km) via subtraction of instrument background (Planck 240 K) to interferograms with added DC signal (right).

Figure 2 Two assumption on bit-discretization of read-out pixels.

Figure 3 Spectral noise example.

Figure 4 Disturbance spectra (examples from Monte-Carlo runs) of digitization noise for the six text cases described in Table 1.

Table 1 Overview of different parameters for the performed tests.

Test #	1	2	3	4	5	6
Bit rounding	14	14	16	14	14	16
Instrument background temperature	10	240	240	10	240	240
Number of A->D pixels converted in a 300 km row	112	112	112	12	12	12

3. Results

Several tests for different parameters for which linear retrieval uncertainty estimations have been performed are provided in Table 1: most are for illustrating the effects of e.g. an ideal instrument with 10 K background temperature or when only 12 large pixels will be read out instead of 112. Therefore, the most 'realistic' cases are provided as test # 2 and 3 with test # 2 being the most realistic one provided the information on instrumental specification.

Figure 4 shows the different additional noise contributions resulting from the A-D conversion:

- The higher the bit-depth, the less the noise
- Higher instrument background increases the dynamic range to which the A-D converter is normalized, thus resulting in higher noise
- A higher number of sub-samples reduces the noise because of averaging (averaging A-D converted noisy signals are less noisy than A-D converted averaged signals)

Figure 5 to Figure 7 show the altitude-dependent profiles of the ratios between discretization error and spectral noise error in case of threshold L2 vertical resolution is assumed for temperature and each of the target species. Each of the columns represents one of the six test cases from Table 1. Comparing the different columns, it is obvious that the discretization error follows the error spectra from Figure 4.

Inspecting the 2nd column, i.e. the most representative one for the instrument, one can see the strongest contribution of the discretization noise in case of NO, CO, NO₂ and H₂O (at upper altitudes). This can be explained by the fact that the spectral signatures of these gases lie in the short-wavelength band of CAIRT (above 1600 cm⁻¹), entirely (NO and CO) or partly (NO₂, H₂O) at higher altitudes (see Figure 9). Since in the calculations above, the simulation was performed for a single-band instrument covering the entire wavenumber range, the DC-value derived as well as the IFG peak height is overestimated compared to an instrument with two bands (due to the spectral behavior of the Planck-function). To take this into account, a further simulation was performed exclusively for the short-wavelength band. The results from this calculation for the cases of CO and NO in case of tests #2 and #3 are shown in Figure 8. These illustrate the strong reduction of discretization noise when a two -band instrument configuration is applied. The same is valid in case of NO₂ and H₂O at altitudes where lines in the short wavelength band are used, (not shown here).

4. Conclusions

- The discretization-noise due to A-D conversion depends strongly on the number of read-pixels converted due to the fact that spectral noise and averaging helps to recover bit-discretization effects.
- Also, the correct DC-level and instrumental background have a strong influence.
- For the assumptions chosen for these parameters in the current test, a 14-bit conversion of the measured IFGs seems to be acceptable when compared to the spectral noise. However, this first evaluation has to be taken with caution and more work to be done with more dedicated and realistic instrument models. Here one has to realistically simulate the instrumental background and number of sub-samples as well as the horizontal and possible vertical binning specific for each of the L2 parameters.

Figure 5 Linear error estimation for the six test cases (columns) from Table 1. Shown are the altitude-dependent profiles of the ratio between discretization error and spectral noise error in case threshold L2 vertical resolution is assumed (mind that in case of CO and NO, the discretization error is overestimated due to the case that a one-band instrument has been used).

Figure 6 As Figure 5 for further species.

Figure 7 As Figure 5 for further species.

Figure 8 Same as Figure 5 but for a two band instrument for species CO and NO. Shown are test # 2 (first column) and # 3 (second column) of the tests described in Table 1.

Figure 9 Altitude-dependent spectral windows used for retrievals. X-axis: wavenumber (cm^{-1}), y-axis: tangent altitude (km).